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**ADDRESSING GLOBAL TERRORIST
FINANCING, RECRUITMENT AND
SPREAD OF TERRORIST NARRATIVES
ON DIGITAL PLATFORMS**

Committe:

UNITED NATIONS SECURITY COUNCIL

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FAHAD HAYAT

INAM UL HAQ

UNDER SECRETARY GENERAL:

Labor Omnia Vincit" : As Virgil was illustrative of the hegemony of Octavian in the 'Georgics'; Fahad Hayat is a stark antithetical embodying the virtues of temperance and justice.

A remarkable asset to the school by not only representing it in various competitions but also by serving as the deputy head boy; Fahad is not afraid to widen his horizons by trying to outgrow his fears as for him "The seed which is not willing to let its shell rot cannot bear fruit".

Apart from winning accolades, Fahad has a penchant for international politics especially matters related to the Middle East. Find him moderating your committee at Mun'Gulberg, or embarking on his next business venture.

ASSISTANT COMMITTEE DIRECTOR:

People are oft akin to a grain of millet in substance, and a turn of a wimple in duration. They fade, obscure and rescind. Oft has such a thought plagued the genteel albeit contriving mind of Inam.

His sword is long; his pen is keen. The countless starts of heavens field, mirror upon his brow- for ambition makes the man, and this one embodies the effigy.

He likens himself to a persona non Grata- having been to eight different schools albeit being an ardent fan of F1 certainly dilutes the lachrymose sentience that underpins most occurrences. Outside the committee room, you'll find him engrossed in enacting a plot to perpetuate the corporate takeover of the civilised world.

Meet the boy, destined to be king- The ACD of UNSC: Inam.

INTRODUCTION TO COMMITTEE

PAS DE DEUX: PERDITION AND PURGATORY

The United Nations Security Council (UNSC) is one of the six principal organs of the United Nations (UN), charged with ensuring international peace and security, recommending the admission of new UN members to the General Assembly, and approving any changes to the UN Charter. Its powers include establishing peacekeeping operations, enacting international sanctions, and authorizing military action. The UNSC is the only UN body with the authority to issue binding resolutions on member states.

INTRODUCTION TO COMMITTEE

INTRODUCTION

The United Nations Security Council was established on October 24th 1945. The UN Security Council is the preeminent worldwide organization for ensuring international peace and security, but it is under constant scrutiny for change in order to better address the challenges of the twenty-first century. The Security Council, the main body of the United Nations for crisis management, has the authority to impose binding obligations on the 193 UN member nations to maintain peace. The UNSC is responsible for reinforcing peace-making operations, establishing international sanctions, authorizing military action and determining the future of any risk against international security. The five permanent members of the council and the ten elected members meet regularly to analyze worldwide security risks such as civil conflicts, natural catastrophes, arms proliferation, and terrorism. Members' opposing interests have frequently hampered the council's capacity to respond to significant conflicts and crises in recent years, such as Syria's civil war, Russia's annexation of Crimea, and the coronavirus epidemic. The Security Council's 5 permanent members (or P5 countries) consists of the United States of America, United Kingdom, Russia, China and France; these permanent members have the power to veto any resolutions brought forward. The 10 rotating members of the Security Council are elected by the General Assembly for a term of 2 years. The Security Council differs from other committees in the way that they have their own rules and regulations.

The first session took place on January 17, 1946, in Westminster, London. UN interventions are authorized by the Security Council on the basis of a mandate which specifies the activities that the operation will do once it is deployed.

The mandate serves as the foundation for all UN peacekeeping operations. Article 24, lays the Mandate of the Security Council. According to this clause, the Organization's members "confer on the Security Council primary responsibility for the maintenance of international peace and security, and agree that in carrying out its duties under this responsibility the Security Council acts on their behalf". Most crucially in this context, the Council is given this jurisdiction in order to ensure prompt and effective. The law further states that in carrying out these responsibilities, the Security Council is obligated to operate in conformity with the goals and objectives of The United Nations. The Security Council's unique powers provided for the performance of these tasks is outlined in Chapters VI-XII of the UN Charter. Of particular interest is article 39 in Chapter VII. According to the prerequisites in this article, the Council is required to adopt decisions in order to preserve or restore international peace and security. Article 25 requires members of the UN to adopt and carry out such decisions.

TERRORISM'S PURPOSE AND MODUS OPERANDI

Terrorism is a daily threat to not only some individuals or countries but a threat on an international level. Hijackings, bombings, assassinations etc. worldwide may appear to be isolated events, but the politics behind them go very deep. Not only is terrorism an instrument to create domination and rebellion, but a way to promote political and religious change through propaganda and violence.

Terrorism relies on fear; terrorist organizations attack innocent people to create fear and terror in the people. The psychological impact of terrorism outweighs the related physical consequences. Terrorist organizations tend to use propaganda through action and social media to increase their influence and following.

Terrorism spreads into several branches for example domestic or international terrorism, non-state terrorism, economic terrorism and cyberterrorism. Terrorism not only requires money to finance illicit actions but also entails a hierarchal and task specific structure in order for good internal communication for higher efficiency which tend to make their actions covert and difficult for national and international authorities to detect.

Financing is one of the most important things terrorist organizations require to conduct their actions. The Central Intelligence Agency claims that before the 9/11 attacks, Al-Qaida required more than \$30 million dollars annually to sustain its actions. These expenses of Al-Qaida included but were not limited to the funding of operations, military training, buying equipment, funding the Taliban and other terrorist organizations.

INTRODUCTION TO THE TOPIC AREA

Since the late 1980s, the Internet has proven to be a very dynamic medium of communication, reaching a global audience that is constantly expanding. The advancement of more advanced technology has resulted in the creation of a network with a genuinely global reach and relatively low entrance barriers. Individuals may now easily access information thanks to advances in Internet technology, to engage with a nearly limitless audience across boundaries in relative anonymity, quickly and efficiently. The advantages of Internet technology are numerous, beginning with given its distinct aptitude for exchanging information and ideas, which is acknowledged as a fundamental human right. However, it should be noted that the same technology that facilitates such communication can also be used for criminal purposes. terrorism. In the battle against terrorism, the use of the Internet for terrorist aims provides both obstacles and possibilities.

Terrorist propaganda published through the Internet serves a variety of purposes and audiences. It can be tailored to future or current supporters or opponents of an organisation or a shared radical viewpoint, to direct or indirect victims of terrorist operations, or to the general public, worldwide society or a portion of it. Messages showing pride, success, and loyalty to an extreme cause may be utilised in propaganda directed at potential or present followers to promote recruitment, radicalization, and incitement to terrorism. According to the U.S Department of Defense, the definition of terrorism is "The calculated use of unlawful violence or threat of unlawful violence to inculcate fear; intended to coerce or to intimidate governments or societies in the pursuit of goals that are generally political, religious, or ideological."

The Milgram experiment presented proof of ordinary people's violent propensity when they are forced to obey or act under an authoritative power. Physiologically, people prefer to belong to groups, group memberships are preserved as a universal characteristic; this includes members capabilities to influence the group, dependency, a common social identity and some sort of a hierarchial connection among group members, despite the functions of the group. One of the most protrusive terrorist groups using the power of the internet to acquire potential political and military strength is Al Qaeda.

Al Qaeda is known to cause imminent intergroup confrontations; a worldwide war on terror, and maybe a "clash of civilizations". The group has made efforts to grasp modern technology, despite its efforts to restore what its members regard as an idealized past and escape the risks of industrialization, globalisation, and democratisation that threaten to destabilise established ways. The extremist groups' strategy includes making online recruiting of terrorist supporters and terrorist operatives possible by utilising a variety of new media platforms.

HISTORY/BACKGROUND OF THE TOPIC

Before the French Revolution, ancient thinkers discussed tyrannicide because tyranny was considered the greatest political threat to Greco-Roman civilization. Mediaeval philosophers were also concerned with the concept of tyranny, although some theologians such as Thomas Aquinas distinguished between usurpers, who could be killed by anyone, and legitimate rulers who abused their power—the later, according to Aquinas, could only be punished by a public authority. The first Christian scholar of the Middle Ages to advocate tyranny was John of Salisbury. Most contemporary academics associate the beginnings of terrorism with the Jewish Sicarii Zealots who lived in 1st century Palestine. They trace its history from the Persian Order of the Assassins to the 19th-century anarchists. "Reign of terror" is commonly regarded as an etymological difficulty.

Since the anarchist movement of the nineteenth century, the term "terrorism" has often been used to characterise violence by non-state actors rather than state action.

As a result of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, the Northern Ireland conflict, the Basque struggle, and the actions of groups such as the Red Army Faction, the terms "terrorism" and "terrorist" took on new currency in the 1970s. In a 1970 issue of Life magazine, Leila Khaled was described as a terrorist. Many books were written about terrorism in the 1970s. With the 1983 Beirut barracks bombings, the September 11, 2001 attacks, and the 2002 Bali bombings, the issue gained prominence. Recent history, especially the last decade, has produced several examples of the mutually beneficial relationship between terrorist organisations and the media.

As several notable terrorist attacks in history demonstrate, whether in the United States (US), Europe, or the Middle East, terrorist architects often use the media to enhance their operational effectiveness, espionage, recruitment, fundraising, and propaganda. To this end, terrorists carefully select the sites of their attacks to maximise media exposure. The obvious example is the September 11 attacks in the United States, which were immediately covered by a wide range of media outlets. Not only was the media able to follow this very graphic attack, but the residents and visitors of New York City were able to document the incident with photographs, films, and personal experiences. The leader of al-Qaeda says that "[al-Qaeda is] in a battle, and more than half of this battle is taking place in the battlefield of the media. [Al-Qaeda is] in a media battle for the hearts and minds of the ummah" The terrorists' methods of communication are very different. Indeed, technological improvements and changing audience behaviour over the past decade have made it easier for terrorists to use media tools. In particular, in the years following the fall of the Berlin Wall and the collapse of the Soviet Union, the means of mass communication have changed dramatically, largely thanks to the global reach of the Internet and mobile phones. Thanks to the new and evolving media, terrorists can now easily spread their messages through websites around the world.

"New technologies have simply allowed terrorist communications to reach a larger audience with a more concise message." According to Moutot, "Terrorists no longer need [print media] to spread their message."

The 'official' media has been supplanted by the Internet, which is ultimately easier to use, much faster, and much more effective. In other words, the Internet has arguably replaced the print media's function in terrorism because, for the first time in history, terrorists can take any message or image they want directly to the online world, which has a global reach. Terrorists are explicitly exploiting this notoriety for their recruitment efforts, as their stories and messages reach the general public, whether through "old" or "new" media. In summary, the Internet has undoubtedly increased the scope of terrorist propaganda and operations and has become an ideal tool for terrorists to promote their operations.

CURRENT SITUATION

Finance and movement of funds are crucial to any terrorist organisation. Regular sources of finance are as important as ideology and the ready supply of recruits for terror organizations. Terrorist organizations require funding to conduct their operations, structural and maintenance cost, recruitment, travel cost, propaganda, communication, training, equipment, indoctrination and surveillance etc. The attacks on Bali, Madrid and London i.e the Bali Nightclub attack had an estimated cost of more than \$50,000, the train bombing in Madrid (2004) cost around \$15000 and the London attack on the tube systems cost around \$2000. Terrorists nowadays have been more and more interested in weapons of mass destruction. Al-Qaeda has interest in developing and using biological weapons which they did in an anthrax laboratory before the US invasion of Afghanistan.

Along with this they have shown interests in chemical weapons such as the use of hydrogen cyanide which they tested on animals in their camps. For this terrorist organizations such as Al-Qaeda require a lot of terror financing.

In Europe, in recent times, isolated religious fundamentalist actors have decided to act and require terror financing in order to properly function. These new types of isolated terrorism are low cost and are financed by their crime activities but often times small terrorist activities tend to grow into large scale terrorist activities.

In order for terrorist organizations to prevail, recruitment is a necessity. Not only does it enable them to recruit future terrorists, killers, suicide bombers, weapons engineers, but recruitment allows them to expand more and more creating more influence on the world. The basis for rapid recruitment of terrorists is the internet specifically social media platforms like twitter, Facebook etc. The internet is a global platform enabling worldwide communication which causes opportunities for terrorist groups to contact people and spread propaganda for recruitment. Recruitment and spread of terrorist narratives through the internet has become a tool for terrorist organizations.

The internet is a platform for organizations like Al-Qaeda to wage their electronic Jihad in not only the Middle East rather globally which is increased by the digital multiplier effects. The evolving doctrine of electronic Jihad has had a lot of impact on the radicalization of Muslims in Western diaspora communities which has led to stereotypes in relation to Islamophobia.

the internet has served as a platform for organizations to spread extremist ideologies like jihadist literature on online libraries, repositories etc. which in turn serves as methods of recruitment. This in turn is also a platform for extremist preachers who are part of terrorist organizations to spread propaganda, ideologies, moreover a perfect forum for radical discourse.

The internet has a very significant role for terrorist-related purposes, specifically for inciting prospective cadres to actions leading to violence, for recruiting fighters, for providing training in tactical methods etc, and most importantly, terrorism financing.

Over time, these terrorists have shifted from the World Wide Web to social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter etc. for better communication to increase their efficiency, nonetheless, the internet serves as a significant catalyst for promoting terrorist activities and for the facilitation of their operations.

CASE STUDIES

Al-Qaeda:

The evolution of Al-Qaeda from a small group of several thousands of people to an ideological vanguard terrorist organization consisting of tens of thousands of people is one of the most profound developments in regards to threats to international security. Even though Al-Qaeda's power, control and capability has been severely affected since 2001, the ideology instilled by Osama bin Laden has catalyzed proliferation of Jihadist groups around the globe which have led to a lot of terrorist attacks over the past few years. These attacks have been carried out by different terrorist groups who were inspired and assisted by Al-Qaeda like in the Middle East and Asia. Since the beginning, Al-Qaeda has used multiple methods to finance their terrorist acts. One of the methods used by Al-Qaeda is fundraisers; these donors are mainly from the Gulf area especially Saudi Arabia.

The donors are sometimes enlightened with the purpose of their funds and are sometimes not. These fundings also come from the secret employees of Al-Qaeda in charitable organizations like that in Ramadan.

Al-Qaeda tends to use Islamic teachings and mend them in such a way as to receive a huge sum of money for e.g. they approach Imams and collect Zakat and use it for their own needs. These fundraisers organized by Al-Qaeda have used legitimate fundraising organizations and legitimate businesses to provide cover for their illegal activities. This has enabled Al-Qaeda to create a large financial network through fundraisers in the whole of the Muslim world and even in foreign diasporas giving them a global reach.

With the rapid spread of the ideologies instilled by Al-Qaeda through social media, these donations have increased globally, including the hitherto un-approached and remote places like the villages in North India.

Al-Qaeda has also used commercial companies to not only finance themselves but also to transfer their funds. Osama bin Laden used to use a network of companies called Barakaat which operated in more than 40 countries in 2001 regarding telecommunications, money transfer and exchange from the United States to Somalia.

At the time of Osama bin Laden, organizations like Barakaat managed and distributed the money of Al-Qaeda and for more efficient work, he linked those transfers with NGOs to hide his network of finance.

Al-Qaeda, despite already having multiple ways to finance their acts, indulges in crimes like kidnapping, ransom and most importantly drug trafficking in countries like Mali and Algeria. These activities make it hard to differentiate between terror finance and common criminal activities like terrorist financing.

State-sponsored terrorism has become a huge problem; India claims that Inter-Services Intelligence {Pakistan} has been sponsoring jihadist groups like Al-Qaeda through the aid they get from the United States. This money is used to finance terrorist organizations like Al-Qaeda for it to function properly.

There is a possibility that Al-Qaeda gets its funds from the countries in the Gulf which need to be investigated and tackled in order to reduce terrorism.

Al-Qaeda's uses the internet specifically social media platforms to spread propaganda for recruitment and sometimes clandestine recruitment in order to keep their illicit acts a secret. The internet provides Al-Qaeda with a global reach for potential recruits and along with this, provides a venue for recruits to learn about and engage with terrorist objectives. The internet also increases the complexity of tracking terrorism-related activity by law enforcement etc. due to technological advancements.

Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan (Taliban):

In the mid-twentieth century, Afghans believed their nation could be a model of economic and social development that would inspire the world. Instead, political conflict, foreign invasion, and civil war have left the country impoverished and politically dysfunctional. It was hoped to see Afghanistan become a more just and democratic nation. But their visions for their country were radically different, and in the end, all plans failed. Now, Afghanistan is associated with international terrorism, drug trafficking, and repression.

The Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan, commonly known as the Taliban, was formed during the Soviet-Afghan war majorly from the Pashtun ethnicity (1994). The Taliban came out as one of the most dominant factor in the Afghan civil war due to the Pashtun dominance in Afghanistan of more than 40% and ever since then, has been a major stakeholder in the politics of Afghanistan. Now the Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan serves as the de facto rulers of Afghanistan after a 20 year long battle with the US and NATO forces post 9/11 attacks till the US withdrawal.

One of the most controversial and important aspect that needs to be understood is the financing of the Taliban. There are multiple ways the Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan is funded; the United States and India have accused countries like Pakistan, Iran and Russia to having given financial aid to the Taliban who have denied all accusations. Private citizens from the Gulf countries are also blamed to be the largest individual contributors to the Taliban cause. Although it is not known how much exactly does the Taliban receive from foreign aid but the US intelligence reported in 2008 that the Taliban received more than \$106 million mostly from the Gulf States.

The Taliban is involved in illegal drug trade which is a major source of finance for them; Afghanistan is the largest producer of opium which is used to make heroin and with an overall export value of more than \$2b dollars, opium is a big business worldwide exploited by the Taliban in Afghanistan. The Taliban is estimated to earn more than \$300 million annually from illicit drug trade.

The Taliban's economic and financial network is larger than just being dependent on opium businesses. The Taliban now controls almost all major trade routes of Afghanistan including border crossings which gives them more revenue from import and export alongside taxations on trade etc.

Afghanistan is a mineral enriched country; a major percentage of the minerals and stones in Afghanistan are untouched due to years of conflict. The mining industry existing in Afghanistan makes over \$1 billion which is majorly consisting of illegal mining.

The United Nations Analytical Support and Sanctions Monitoring team in its 2014 annual report reported that the Taliban earn more than \$10 million dollars annually from illegal mining operations from the Helmand.

The Taliban finance their actions through these methods and in order to tackle terrorism, there is a need to cut off the terror finance supply of the Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan.

The Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan has transitioned from newspapers and radio for recruitment and propaganda to modern communication technologies, social media and smartphone applications etc. The Taliban use the internet as a basis for relentless propaganda campaigns posting videos, announcing leaderships on platforms like Facebook. These are now a very important part of the Taliban's political and military strategy to win over the public opinion and to gain support for recruitment and ensuring loyalty.

In addition to using social media as a recruitment tool, the Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan use Facebook to identify and neutralize opponents in Afghanistan to ensure loyalty through fear in the hearts of the people.

Hezbollah:

Entering the Lebanese government in 2009 and the recent forceful intervention in the Syrian civil war by Hezbollah, the Shi'i political and military party continues to influence in the Middle East. Post Islamic revolution, a group of Lebanese Shi'i clerics formed Hezbollah with the goal of driving Israel from Lebanon in 1979 and establishing an Islamic republic over there. The United States and Israel denounce it as a dangerous terrorist group and have refused to engage with the party.

It is not clear how Hezbollah is financed but there are some rumors on how they are funded. Iran is believed to fund Hezbollah of at least more than \$100 million annually and Western diplomats estimate that the funding has been increased up to \$200 million annually.

It is rumoured that in the wake of the death of Yasser Arafat {Palestinian leader}, Hezbollah received an additional \$22 million from Iranian intelligence to support the so-called Palestinian terrorist groups to cause instability in the West Bank and Gaza.

Iran was also reported to have financed and established terrorist training camps in the Syrian-controlled Bekaa Valley to train Hezbollah, Hamas, PIJ and PFLP-GC terrorists to use rockets such as the short range Fajr-5 missile and the SA-7 anti-aircraft rocket.

Along with financing from countries like Iran, Hezbollah also uses money writing companies like the Western Union to not only launder and transfer funds but also to raise money for e.g Hezbollah funded Palestinian groups in the West Bank via Western Union which consisted of more than \$3 million in 2003-2004 alone. Hezbollah activists run Western Union offices and share the profits with Hezbollah.

Along with these, Hezbollah receives significant financial support from the contributions of Hezbollah supporters living abroad, particularly from Lebanese nationals living in Africa, South America and other places with large Lebanese Shia expatriate communities. Hezbollah's main income, according to Hezbollah Parliamentarian Mohammad Raad, comes from the groups own investment portfolios and wealthy Shias which enables them to function properly.

Hezbollah also uses charity and fundraising organizations to conceal its fundraising activities although it is less reliant compared to groups like Hamas because of its annual subsidies from Iran and other significant involvement in criminal enterprises.

In recent times, Hezbollah has used social media as a platform to recruit Israeli Arabs and West Bank Palestinians; the new change in terrorist tactics has given rise to virtual entrepreneurs which have been associated with the online recruitment efforts of not only Hezbollah but other organizations as well. Hezbollah's virtual planners use social media to establish contact with potential recruits and then transition towards more encrypted communications platforms, transfer funds and issue instructions etc. Online recruitment presents a low-cost option that offers plausible deniability for Hezbollah. By digitally recruiting Palestinians to fight Israelis, Hezbollah and Iran are seeking to cultivate a new front against Israel amid rising regional hostilities.

Boko Haram:

Nigeria has had a long and unfortunate history of communal conflicts and ethnoreligious violence which has caused a lot of instability in the region. Weaknesses in the already flawed institutions of politics and security services has a created a political situation where such threats to the stability are not deescalated and properly dealt with until violence is a certainty. It is a general phenomenon that only when a politician in control of a state is convinced that such a threat cannot be bent to his advantage will he order any action be taken against it. Such are the flaws existing in the security institutions of Nigeria that their only way of dealing any sort of threat is to involve violence. Under this situation was the birth of Boko Haram.

Boko Haram is an Islamic organization that believes that the northern politics are influenced by corrupt, false Muslims. Its main aim is to wage war and to establish Sharia law in Nigeria and since 2009, has been driven by a desire to fight and counter politicians, police and authorities for their role in suppression of the group. Boko Haram has proven to be very adaptable evolving its tactics and improvising for more efficiency. Boko Haram became a global concern in 2011 when it was responsible for conducting a bombing in the United Nations compound in Abuja killing 23 people.

The speed at which the group developed the capability to produce large and effective improvised explosive devices and enlist suicide bombers to deliver them suggests outside help. But thus far there remains no sign to say that Boko Haram aims to confront and attack Western interests inside or outside Nigeria.

Boko Haram is the largest terrorist organization in Africa; the United Nations in one of their report disclosed that the activities of Boko Haram are funded through multiple sources such as taxes, extortions, robberies, charitable donations, smuggling, kidnapping and ransoms, and foreign remittances.

Kidnap-for-ransom is now one of the major source of financing for Boko Haram, a lucrative enterprise that has now become a full-blown industry under Boko Haram.

Another source of financing for Boko Haram is commercial fishing and farming of red pepper. It is reported that Boko Haram is in complete control of the fishing activities in Baga and are said to be in charge of the fishing trade of most of the region and thus, to for the local people to get fishing rights, they are required to make payments to Boko Haram which finances their actions.

It is rumoured that the politicians from Northern Nigeria including the governors etc. pay protection money to Boko Haram although the politicians deny it publicly. It is also said that the politicians use these extremist groups to rig the elections as well.

The expansion of Boko Haram in Nigeria in the last few years has been drastic; its military activity has increased to more severity of attacks, a wider geographic scope, target-based killings and the evolution of strategies and tactics.

The changes and evolution include the development of ties with Al-Qaeda, exploitation of the border area that separates Nigeria from its neighbours and strong-armed operations.

There are psychological, ideological, philosophical, political and socioeconomic factors that lead people, especially the youth to participate in terrorist and violent extremist groups.

Boko Haram uses religious institutions especially madrassas to recruit members; religious schools are the venue where most individuals are radicalized and recruited. About 12.6% of Boko Haram members are recruited in madrassas {12.5% of male and 2.7% of female}.

Figure 15: Religious institutions

In addition to being furthest off the mark on the role religious institutions play in the recruitment process, peacebuilders to a large degree overestimated the role the internet, including social media and schools, plays in the recruitment process. It is often agreed that radicalization is done online; even though a lot of interviewed Boko Haram members deny that recruitment occurs online sometimes, more than 5.9% members agreed upon the fact that Boko Haram does recruit online.

Figure 17: Broader community

PAST UN ACTION

1. Ten years ago, the UN General Assembly adopted a Global Counter-Terrorism Strategy.

2. 1999 Convention on Terrorist Financing

3. Sanctions were imposed on the Taliban administration in Afghanistan in 1999 for harbouring Al Qaida leadership.

4. One of the most groundbreaking resolutions in the body's history, Resolution 1373. It put legally enforceable requirements on all UN member nations to improve laws, reinforce border controls, and promote international collaboration to combat terrorism, among other things.

5. The Council formally passed resolution 2462 (2019) under Chapter VII of the United Nations Charter, reaffirming its resolution 1373 (2001) – adopted in the aftermath of the 11 September 2001 attacks in the United States – which requires all States to avert and subdue terrorist financing and to refrain from providing support to those involved in it.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

1. 1.94.7 per cent of terrorists or terrorist organizations attempt to recruit people over the internet.

2. The comparable result that lone-actors who attempted to attract others (but failed) were 5.00 times more likely to have learnt online supports this interpretation:

- The bivariate study also found differences in affordance consumption based on the offender's immediate co-offending network. Individuals were 2.64 times more likely to learn online than cell members. This might be because, within a cell, there is most likely a pooling of human, social, technological, and financial resources, the absence of which motivates people to go online to learn how to conduct assaults and for other purposes.

3. Propaganda distribution accounted for 48% of the criminals apprehended.

4. 15% of actors use the internet to propagate their agenda.

DEBATE DIRECTION

- To discuss the role of transnational corporations and business enterprises on the issue of global terrorist financing, recruitment and spread of terrorist narratives on digital platforms.
- To discuss methods to meliorate global terrorist financing, recruitment and spread of terrorist narratives on digital platforms.
- To discuss the effects of foreign debt and other external financial obligations in having an adverse effect on global terrorist financing, recruitment and spread of terrorist narratives on digital platforms.
- To discuss possible frameworks in countering global terrorist financing, recruitment and spread of terrorist narratives on digital platforms.
- To discuss the role of UN.
- To discuss the role of Inter Govt. bodies.
- To discuss the elimination of global terrorist financing, recruitment and spread of terrorist narratives on digital platforms.
- Definitions.

- Types of terrorism.
- Terrorism in the aspects of the international law.
- Specific human rights challenges in the context of terrorism and counter-terrorism.
- How fighting counter-terrorism can result in the violation of the human rights of the civilians.

- Differentiating International Terrorism and People's struggle for self-determination.
- The Applicability of the international humanitarian law.
- Violation of child rights.
- Violation of women rights.
- Cyberattacks.
- Background of the topic.
- History of the topic.
- United Nations Resolutions and their loopholes.
- Solutions towards the protection of child rights during counter-terrorism.
- How the right to privacy can be ensured while countering terrorism?
- To discuss international refugee law migration and counter-terrorism.
- Counter-terrorism and the use of conventional weapons.
- Criminal justice responses to terrorism.

PAST UN RESOLUTIONS

Security Council

Distr.: General

28 September 2001

Resolution 1373 (2001)

**Adopted by the Security Council at its 4385th meeting, on
28 September 2001**

The Security Council,

Reaffirming its resolutions 1269 (1999) of 19 October 1999 and 1368 (2001) of 12 September 2001,

Reaffirming also its unequivocal condemnation of the terrorist attacks which took place in New York, Washington, D.C. and Pennsylvania on 11 September 2001, and expressing its determination to prevent all such acts,

Reaffirming further that such acts, like any act of international terrorism, constitute a threat to international peace and security,

Reaffirming the inherent right of individual or collective self-defence as recognized by the Charter of the United Nations as reiterated in resolution 1368 (2001),

Reaffirming the need to combat by all means, in accordance with the Charter of the United Nations, threats to international peace and security caused by terrorist acts,

Deeply concerned by the increase, in various regions of the world, of acts of terrorism motivated by intolerance or extremism,

Calling on States to work together urgently to prevent and suppress terrorist acts, including through increased cooperation and full implementation of the relevant international conventions relating to terrorism,

Recognizing the need for States to complement international cooperation by taking additional measures to prevent and suppress, in their territories through all lawful means, the financing and preparation of any acts of terrorism,

Reaffirming the principle established by the General Assembly in its declaration of October 1970 (resolution 2625 (XXV)) and reiterated by the Security Council in its resolution 1189 (1998) of 13 August 1998, namely that every State has the duty to refrain from organizing, instigating, assisting or participating in terrorist acts in another State or acquiescing in organized activities within its territory directed towards the commission of such acts,

Acting under Chapter VII of the Charter of the United Nations,

1. *Decides* that all States shall:

- (a) Prevent and suppress the financing of terrorist acts;
- (b) Criminalize the wilful provision or collection, by any means, directly or indirectly, of funds by their nationals or in their territories with the intention that the funds should be used, or in the knowledge that they are to be used, in order to carry out terrorist acts;
- (c) Freeze without delay funds and other financial assets or economic resources of persons who commit, or attempt to commit, terrorist acts or participate in or facilitate the commission of terrorist acts; of entities owned or controlled directly or indirectly by such persons; and of persons and entities acting on behalf of, or at the direction of such persons and entities, including funds derived or generated from property owned or controlled directly or indirectly by such persons and associated persons and entities;
- (d) Prohibit their nationals or any persons and entities within their territories from making any funds, financial assets or economic resources or financial or other related services available, directly or indirectly, for the benefit of persons who commit or attempt to commit or facilitate or participate in the commission of terrorist acts, of entities owned or controlled, directly or indirectly, by such persons and of persons and entities acting on behalf of or at the direction of such persons;

2. *Decides also* that all States shall:

- (a) Refrain from providing any form of support, active or passive, to entities or persons involved in terrorist acts, including by suppressing recruitment of members of terrorist groups and eliminating the supply of weapons to terrorists;
- (b) Take the necessary steps to prevent the commission of terrorist acts, including by provision of early warning to other States by exchange of information;
- (c) Deny safe haven to those who finance, plan, support, or commit terrorist acts, or provide safe havens;
- (d) Prevent those who finance, plan, facilitate or commit terrorist acts from using their respective territories for those purposes against other States or their citizens;
- (e) Ensure that any person who participates in the financing, planning, preparation or perpetration of terrorist acts or in supporting terrorist acts is brought to justice and ensure that, in addition to any other measures against them, such terrorist acts are established as serious criminal offences in domestic laws and regulations and that the punishment duly reflects the seriousness of such terrorist acts;
- (f) Afford one another the greatest measure of assistance in connection with criminal investigations or criminal proceedings relating to the financing or support of terrorist acts, including assistance in obtaining evidence in their possession necessary for the proceedings;
- (g) Prevent the movement of terrorists or terrorist groups by effective border controls and controls on issuance of identity papers and travel documents, and through measures for preventing counterfeiting, forgery or fraudulent use of identity papers and travel documents;

3. *Calls upon all States to:*

(a) Find ways of intensifying and accelerating the exchange of operational information, especially regarding actions or movements of terrorist persons or networks; forged or falsified travel documents; traffic in arms, explosives or sensitive materials; use of communications technologies by terrorist groups; and the threat posed by the possession of weapons of mass destruction by terrorist groups;

(b) Exchange information in accordance with international and domestic law and cooperate on administrative and judicial matters to prevent the commission of terrorist acts;

(c) Cooperate, particularly through bilateral and multilateral arrangements and agreements, to prevent and suppress terrorist attacks and take action against perpetrators of such acts;

(d) Become parties as soon as possible to the relevant international conventions and protocols relating to terrorism, including the International Convention for the Suppression of the Financing of Terrorism of 9 December 1999;

(e) Increase cooperation and fully implement the relevant international conventions and protocols relating to terrorism and Security Council resolutions 1269 (1999) and 1368 (2001);

(f) Take appropriate measures in conformity with the relevant provisions of national and international law, including international standards of human rights, before granting refugee status, for the purpose of ensuring that the asylum-seeker has not planned, facilitated or participated in the commission of terrorist acts;

(g) Ensure, in conformity with international law, that refugee status is not abused by the perpetrators, organizers or facilitators of terrorist acts, and that claims of political motivation are not recognized as grounds for refusing requests for the extradition of alleged terrorists;

4. *Notes with concern* the close connection between international terrorism and transnational organized crime, illicit drugs, money-laundering, illegal arms-trafficking, and illegal movement of nuclear, chemical, biological and other potentially deadly materials, and in this regard *emphasizes* the need to enhance coordination of efforts on national, subregional, regional and international levels in order to strengthen a global response to this serious challenge and threat to international security;

5. *Declares* that acts, methods, and practices of terrorism are contrary to the purposes and principles of the United Nations and that knowingly financing, planning and inciting terrorist acts are also contrary to the purposes and principles of the United Nations;

6. *Decides* to establish, in accordance with rule 28 of its provisional rules of procedure, a Committee of the Security Council, consisting of all the members of the Council, to monitor implementation of this resolution, with the assistance of appropriate expertise, and *calls upon* all States to report to the Committee, no later than 90 days from the date of adoption of this resolution and thereafter according to a timetable to be proposed by the Committee, on the steps they have taken to implement this resolution;

7. *Directs* the Committee to delineate its tasks, submit a work programme within 30 days of the adoption of this resolution, and to consider the support it requires, in consultation with the Secretary-General;

8. *Expresses* its determination to take all necessary steps in order to ensure the full implementation of this resolution, in accordance with its responsibilities under the Charter;

9. *Decides* to remain seized of this matter.

BLOC POSITIONS

In regard to the topic, the bloc position would be reliant on the direction that the delegates opt for. Even though there will be no proper fixed bloc positioning, there are some points that will help shape the bloc positions in the committee:

1. Firstly, contentions will be based on the definition of terrorism for e.g the US recognizes the Taliban as terrorists but Pakistan does not. This will cause differences between countries leading to different blocs.

2. Secondly, the other possibility is a two bloc system in which the countries which don't recognize the US-recognized terrorists will consist of one bloc and the US supporters {mainly the West} will consist of the other bloc and have contentions on the following:

- a. The different views of the parties on the matter of the definition of terrorism, which would be established as the main contention between the two blocs.

b. Secondly, the opposing views on what defines terror financing, and in some cases the definition of terrorism can lead to:

- i. Clashing views on whether funding of extremist groups is terror financing or not
- ii. Differing views on whether organizations like Taliban, Hezbollah etc are terrorists and whether their actions fall under terrorist actions

3. Delegates may feel free to bring up other contentions to bring up valid contentions upon the basis of the following:

- a. The contention is based upon something which infringes their sovereignty,
- b. The contention is deemed valid if the international conventions are clashing with the constitution of the country
- c. The contention is based upon clashing national policies to an extent where compromise is not possible.
-

In a nutshell, the following bloc positions lay down the basis for the committee to move upon in a systematic order and ensure that the blocs formed do not have contentions that are vague and can be resolved on unity. The contentions must be backed by evidence and instances from the real world.

CONCLUSIVE UNDERSTANDING

The delegates should understand and analyze the situation of terrorism in every important geo-political region possible for achieving a long-lasting and effective solution. They should first analyze the roots of these organizations, should break and analyze their ideologies, and while taking into account the current situation and actions, should present a proper structured framework addressing the following points:

- 1.Functions of the framework
- 2.Organizational structure of the framework
- 3.Relationship between the problem at hand and the framework
- 4.Financing operations of the framework
- 5.Forms of financing
- 6.Role of important stakeholders

The delegates should understand the role of the religious preachers, the states in the specific geographical region which have a role in shaping the politics, the media, social media platforms etc.

The committee should understand how preventing digital recruitment has a risk of infringing the right to privacy; the committee should address and provide proper solutions to tackle the clash between digital security to prevent recruitment and the violations of the right to privacy.

The committee should understand the role of organizations such as NATO, OIC, and the E.U. and the influence of their actions on the problem at hand.

The committee should understand key terminologies such as terrorism, terror financing, digital recruitment because differing definitions can lead to clashing views and perspectives.

While keeping these points in their minds along with ideas of their own, the delegates should approach the problem at hand in a systematic and organized way in order for better efficiency.

POINTS TO REMEMBER

The delegates are advised to research on these points:

- (1) Why Al Qaeda ranks top within global terrorist financing, recruitment and spread of terrorist narratives on digital platforms.
- (2) How global terrorist financing, recruitment and spread of terrorist narratives on digital platforms affects economies.
- (3) Why there is little to zero attention in this space and what can be done to encourage state members to take action.
- (4) Financing and recruitment of other terrorist organizations e.g Hezbollah.
- (5) How ignoring the rise of global terrorist financing, recruitment and spread of terrorist narratives on digital platforms can lead to a catastrophic crisis.
- (6) Methods and techniques terrorist organizations use for terrorist financing, recruitment and spread of terrorist narratives on digital platforms.
- (7) The Struggle of a Democracy against Terrorism - Protection of Human Rights: The Right to Privacy versus the National Interest - the Proper Balance.
- (8) The different forms of financing.

QUESTIONS A RESOLUTION MUST ANSWER

UNITED NATIONS SECURITY COUNCIL

CATEGORY A

1. What is the definition of terrorism, what actions fall under terrorist activities?
2. Why and how does terror financing occur?
3. How to tackle the corruption in organizations like Western Union to restrict terror financing?

CATEGORY B

4. How to counter countries funding terrorist activities?
5. How online platforms such as social media play a significant role in spreading terrorist narratives via propaganda etc?

CATEGORY C

8. How do social media platforms like Facebook etc enable organizations to spread propaganda, instil ideologies and recruit members?
9. How organizations such as OIC, NATO, and EU can play a role in countering these problems?

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